

19 **ABSTRACT**

20 To optimize the sanitation treatment of ready-to-eat (RTE) intermediate moisture
21 foods (IMF), the behaviour of *Listeria monocytogenes* Scott A (CIP 103575), *Listeria*
22 *innocua* (NTC 11288), *Salmonella enterica* serovar Typhimurium and *Escherichia coli*
23 O157:H7 (CECT 4972) against the treatment with E-beam irradiation has been studied.
24 As food matrixes, three RTE vacuum-packed products [Iberian dry-cured ham, dry beef
25 (*cecina*) and smoked tuna] were used. Although, an irradiation treatment is not
26 necessary when the 10² c.f.u/g microbiological criterion for *L. monocytogenes* is
27 applied, a treatment of 1.5 kGy must be applied to IMFs to meet the food safety
28 objective (FSO) in the case of “zero tolerance” criterion for the three strains. The IMF
29 products presented negligible modifications of colour (*L**, *a** and *b**), sensory
30 (appearance, odour and flavour) and rheology (hardness, springiness, adhesiveness,
31 cohesiveness, gumminess, chewiness and breaking strength) parameters at doses lower
32 than 2 kGy. Therefore, the treatment of 1.5 kGy warrants safe IMF with similar sensory
33 properties to the genuine products.

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35 **Keywords:** *S. Typhimurium*, *L. monocytogenes*, *E. coli*, RTE, IMF, E-beam treatment

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37 1. INTRODUCCION

38 The foods considered in this paper under the caption “intermediate moisture
39 foods of animal origin” are meat and fish products with an a_w between 0.83 and 0.90.
40 As models, Iberian dry-cured ham, dry smoked beef (*cecina*) and smoked tuna were
41 selected to be representative of meat products from pig, cow, and fish, respectively.
42 They are all marketed both as whole pieces at room temperature and ready-to-eat (RTE)
43 domestic portions, usually under refrigeration.

44 Most spoilage microorganisms of concern in foods have optimal a_w levels for
45 growth above 0.98. Although many can achieve more than half of their maximum
46 growth rate at 0.98 a_w , some organisms are already inhibited at this level, so that
47 reducing the a_w below 0.98 a_w can have a marked effect on the composition of the
48 microbiota of some foods. This is the case, for example, in dry fermented sausages
49 production where the typical Gram negative bacteria of refrigerated raw meat is
50 replaced by lactic acid bacteria and members of the family *Micrococcaceae* due to the
51 reduction of the a_w from 0.99 to 0.96 as a consequence of the addition of curing salts
52 (salt, nitrates and nitrites and ascorbic acid) and sugars (Ordóñez, Hierro, Bruna, & Hoz,
53 1999). At a lower a_w (less than 0.90 - 0.92) only the growth of Gram positive cocci may
54 be expected. In fact, Leistener & Rödel (1975) included in the category of shelf-stable
55 meat products those with a $\text{pH} \leq 5.2$ and $a_w \leq 0.95$ or only $\text{pH} 5.0$ or only $a_w < 0.90$ in
56 which no refrigeration during storage is required. No bacterial growth is observed at a_w
57 < 0.85 (ICMSF, 1980).

58 With respect to pathogens, the bacteria of most concern in foods at a relative low
59 a_w are *S. aureus* and *L. monocytogenes*. The former may grow even at an a_w as low as
60 0.85 (Troller, & Stinson, 1975) but no enterotoxin production has been detected at an a_w
61 lower than 0.93 (Notermans & Heuvelman, 1983; Smith, Buchanan, & Palumbo, 1983).

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62 Furthermore, the growth of *S. aureus* is very easy to control in refrigerated foods since
63 the lowest temperature it may multiply is 7 °C (Jay, Loessner, & Golden, 2005; Smith *et*
64 *al.*, 1983), at which a very long generation time (68 hours) has been recorded in cooked
65 ham (Cabeza, Cambero, Núñez, Medina, de la Hoz, & Ordóñez, 2010). *L.*
66 *monocytogenes* is a psychrotrophic and ubiquitous bacterium whose limit value for
67 growth is at 0.92 a_w in refrigerated foods regardless of pH (Farber & Harwing, 1996;
68 ICMSF, 1996). In fact, the (EC) No 1441/2007 regulation (CEC, 2007) on
69 microbiological criteria for food established the concentration of *L. monocytogenes* for
70 RTE foods able to support the growth of this bacterium as an absence in 25 g. However,
71 the limit is a concentration below 100 c.f.u./g when *L. monocytogenes* is not able to
72 multiply, thus RTE products with a pH \leq 4.4 or $a_w \leq$ 0.92 or those with a pH \leq 5.0 and
73 $a_w \leq$ 0.94 are automatically included in this category.

74 Iberian dry-cured ham is a cured product made from the whole pork leg of
75 Iberian pig (an indigenous, black-footed, fine skeleton and long-legged breed with
76 adipogenic ability). Its sensory attributes, the manufacturing process and other
77 properties are reported elsewhere (López, Hoz, Cambero, Gallardo, Reglero, &
78 Ordóñez, 1992; Martín, Córdoba, Ventanas, & Antequera, 1999). In the context of this
79 paper, the most interesting phase of dry-cured ham production is when it has been salted
80 and dried (after 6 - 9 months). Afterwards, the hams are dried in cellars in ambient air
81 during 18 – 24 months to reach a total ripening period of over 2 years although its shelf-
82 life may be extended for an additional 4-8 months without any loss of quality (Martin *et*
83 *al.*, 1999). The final product (commonly 6 - 8 kg) presents a pH of about 6.0, an a_w of
84 0.85 - 0.88 and a moisture content of around 45%. The “*cecina*” (Celtic “*ciercina*”
85 means “*cierzo*”, the name of a Northern Iberian wind) is made with muscle pieces (7 -
86 12 kg) from the hind legs of beef. *Cecina* production is also described elsewhere

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87 (García, Zumalacárregui, & Díez, 1995). Briefly, pieces are salted and dried in a similar
88 way to dry-cured ham and they are usually smoked (normally, burning woods from
89 acorn, beech or oak) in adequate rooms and then they are cured for several months. The
90 whole process takes longer than 6 - 8 months. The final pieces (3 - 6 kg) have a pH of
91 close to 6.0, an $a_w < 0.88$ and a moisture content of around 45%. Smoked tuna is made
92 from separated muscle regions of the fish (normally 4 pieces are obtained), which are
93 then cut into strips or chunks (0.5 - 1.5 kg) salted and cured for about a month. The final
94 product present an $a_w < 0.88$ and it is usually sold vacuum-packaged. Considering the
95 a_w of the three products, they may be included in the category of IMF. Therefore, these
96 foods are microbiologically stable and they are endowed with a very long shelf-life,
97 which may be estimated to be over 4 - 6 months. The only possible spoilage may be due
98 to the growth of moulds and fatty acid autooxidation reactions when they are packed in
99 a non-anoxic atmosphere. Likewise, they are of no concern from a public health point of
100 view and their consumption presents no hazard immediately after cutting from the
101 whole piece. Currently, the hygienic background of these products may be regarded as
102 excellent.

103 The problem arises when these foods are transformed into RTE products. This
104 involves several operations, namely, either cutting or slicing, and packing, which
105 increase the contamination risk because a variety of pathogenic microorganisms can
106 reach the food from the environment of the processing industry; tools, handlers, etc.
107 Even when there operations are performed under very strict hygienic conditions, there is
108 no guarantee that the RTE-IMF products will be consistently free of some pathogenic
109 organisms since there is no bactericide step during the process. The pathogens of most
110 concern are those in which the zero tolerance criterion (i.e, absence in 25 g) is applied
111 because they are usually the most harmful pathogens and their detection implies a

112 previous enrichment. Thus, a very low pathogen concentration may be detected. The
113 contamination of a given RTE food by a pathogen of the “tolerance zero” category
114 could lead to its detection and subsequent condemnation. The mere presence of these
115 organisms is of significant concern and may lead to a loss of sales, at best, and, at worst,
116 to serious illness. Among the “tolerance zero” organisms, the most interesting are,
117 undoubtedly, *E. coli* O157:H7, *Salmonella* spp. and *L. monocytogenes*. The former
118 because the infectious dose is very low (Meng, Doyle, Zhao, & Zhao, 2001), it can
119 occur from less than 100 cells (AGA, 1994) to about one dozen or less cells (Tilden *et*
120 *al.*, 1996). The interest in *Salmonella* spp. and *L. monocytogenes* lies in that they are
121 ubiquitous organisms although the latter is only of concern in the case of the USDA
122 regulation, but it lacks significance in the EC regulation (except in foods for infants and
123 special medical purposes) since the bacterium does not growth in IMF. The conversion
124 of the IMF mentioned above into RTE products is performed by slicing processed
125 pieces to yield convenient domestic portions, which are packed in barrier bags in the
126 which inside atmosphere may, or may not be, modified. It is not possible the use of
127 traditional technologies for sanitizing the sliced and packed RTE products.
128 Nevertheless, we have previously demonstrated that the E-beam irradiation is a very
129 effective way to reduce pathogens numbers present in a variety of RTE foods to a safe
130 level (Cabeza, Cambero, Hoz, & Ordóñez, 2007; Cabeza, de la Hoz, Ordóñez, &
131 Cambero, 2009; Cambero, Cabeza, Ordóñez, & Hoz, 2011; Hoz, Cambero, Cabeza,
132 Herrero, & Ordóñez, 2008). Therefore, the present work centers on the sanitation of
133 RTE-IMF products of animal origin exemplified with Iberian dry-cured ham, *cecina*
134 and smoked tuna. This work was focused to carefully adjust the irradiation doses to
135 achieve an adequate level of microbial safety with minimum changes in sensory
136 attributes to avoid rejection of the irradiated product by the consumer.

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138 **2. MATERIAL AND METHODS**

139 *2.1. Estimation of food safety features*

140 The selected IMF are products with an a_w below 0.90, at which no pathogen
141 bacteria may grow, except for *S. aureus*. From a public health point of view, there is no
142 sanitation concern if these foods are consumed immediately after cutting. However,
143 during its transformation into RTE products, several pathogen organisms may
144 contaminate the final product. The reasoning used to assess the potential contamination
145 of a RTE meat product during slicing and packaging has been previously described
146 (Cabeza et al., 2007) and it was concluded that the contamination of cooked ham with
147 *L. monocytogenes* during its transformation into a RTE product can reach, in the worst
148 of cases, 10 cells. This may also be applied to IMF since the same operations have to be
149 performed for its conversion into a RTE product. Since salmonellae are ubiquitous
150 organisms, a comparable degree of contamination may be supposed. Although the
151 contamination of RTE products by *E. coli* O157:H7 is lower and less frequent (about
152 one cell per gram could be assumed) than listeria or salmonellae (Bohaychuk et al.,
153 2006), the same level of contamination may be considered because of the great
154 pathogenic power of this bacterium. Thus, in all cases, the initial level of hazard (H_0) is
155 1 ($\log_{10} 10$).

156 Some health authorities, such as the USDA, recommend a “zero tolerance”
157 policy for *L. monocytogenes* in all RTE products, which means a food safety objective
158 (FSO) of 4 c.f.u./100g ($\log_{10} = - 1.39$). However, given that a stricter tolerance of “not
159 detected in 25 g” does not provide a higher level of protection (Ross, Todd, & Smith,
160 2000), both the ICMSF (2001) and SCVPH (2005) take the view that the criterion could
161 be 100 c.f.u./g ($\log_{10} = 2$) at the time of consumption, when the product is not able to

162 support the growth of *L. monocytogenes* (SCVPH, 2005). The microbiological criterion
163 for *Salmonella* spp. and *E. coli* O157:H7 is an “absence in 25 g” practically all over the
164 world.

165 Since none of the three microorganisms can grow in the IMF product here
166 selected during the shelf-life of the final product, the performance objective [PeO,
167 maximum frequency and/or concentration of a hazard in a food at a specific phase in the
168 food chain before the time of consumption that provides or contributes to an FSO or
169 adequate level of protection, as applicable (Gorris, 2005)] is zero, i.e. there will be no
170 hazard increase regardless of whether the product is going to a market with either the
171 100 c.f.u./g or “zero tolerance” microbiological criterion.

172 Nevertheless, the performance criterion [(PeC, the effect in frequency and/or
173 concentration of a hazard in a food that must be achieved by the application of one or
174 more control measures to provide or contribute to a FSO or adequate level of protection,
175 as applicable (Gorris, 2005)] is not the same for both markets. In the case of 100 c.f.u./g
176 acceptance, no sanitation treatment is necessary since the assumed contamination (10
177 cells/g, $H_0 = 1$) value is lower than the FSO (100 c.f.u./g). In the case of “zero
178 tolerance”, the PeC may be calculated using the expression $FSO = H_0 - PeC + PeO$
179 (ICMSF, 2001) and the mentioned data ($FSO = -1.39$; $H_0 = 1$; $PeO = 0$) with a final
180 result of $PeC = 2.39 D$ reduction of the original load of the three organisms.

181 2.2. *Organisms.*

182 Previously, we have observed (Cabeza et al., 2009) that *S. Typhimurium* is more
183 radioresistant than *S. Enteritidis* in two types of dry fermented sausages (a fermented
184 IMF) with an a_w of 0.88 (decimal reduction of 0.53 kGy vs 0.41 kGy) and 0.80 (0.54
185 kGy vs 0.43 kGy). Accordingly, only *S. Typhimurium* (CECT 443) was used in the
186 present work. One strain of *L. monocytogenes* Scott A (CIP 103575), another of *E. coli*

187 O157:H7 (CECT 4972) and, as a surrogate of *L. monocytogenes*, one strain of *L.*
188 *innocua* (NTC 11288), were also used. The handling, subculture and the inoculum
189 preparation of the salmonella and listeria strains have been previously described
190 (Cabeza et al., 2007; 2009). The inoculum of *E. coli* O157:H7 was prepared in a similar
191 way. The slices of IMF were contaminated by immersion in a beaker for a few seconds.
192 In experiments, a large number of cells were used to precisely calculate the
193 radioresistant parameters.

195 2.3. Sample preparation and irradiation treatment.

196 Pieces (2 - 5 kg weight) of the IMF were purchased in a local market. Then, they
197 were sliced (3 or 15 mm thickness) using an electric machine, whose rotating blade and
198 contact surfaces were previously deeply cleaned. For microbiological, chemical and
199 sensory analysis, slices were prepared following the same procedure than that used
200 previously for dry fermented sausages (Cabeza et al., 2009). Samples were treated with
201 an industrial electron beam radiation source, which operates at 10 MeV, located in
202 Tarancón, Cuenca, Spain. The radiation doses used were between 1 and 3 kGy. The
203 dose absorbed by samples was verified by determining the absorbance of cellulose
204 triacetate dosimeters (ASTM, 2000), simultaneously irradiated. Experiments were
205 performed at room temperature (18 - 20°C) by triplicate. The temperature increase
206 during treatment was less than 2 °C. After irradiation treatment, samples were stored at
207 4 °C until use.

209 2.4. Microbial analysis.

210 Although the bacterial load of the IMF is low, selective media were used to do
211 the survival counts and avoid the growth of natural microbiota. *Salmonella* sp. and *E.*

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212 *coli* sp. were enumerated in red violet glucose agar (RVG) where Gram positive bacteria
213 are unable to growth. To count survivors of *L. innocua* and *L. monocytogenes*, the
214 selective Palcam medium for *Listeria* spp was chosen. To count the survivors, the slices
215 (about 10 g) were homogenized with 10 ml of sterile saline solution in a Stomacher bag,
216 once they were weighed. Counts were determined on the surface of plates by using a
217 spiral plate system (model Eddy Jet, IUL Instrument, Barcelona, Spain). Plates were
218 incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. Colonies were enumerated with an automatic counter
219 (model Counterstat Flash, IUL Instrument, Barcelona, Spain).

220 The shelf-life of irradiated samples was only studied in the smoked tuna since it
221 was the IMF product with the highest a_w (0.88). It was determined by periodically
222 counting the bacterial number in samples stored at 4 °C. Non-irradiated samples were
223 used as controls.

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225 *2.5. Physic-chemical analyses, colour measurement, texture profile analysis (TPA),*
226 *tensile test and sensory analysis.*

227 The performance of these analyses is extensively described in previous articles
228 (Cabeza et al., 2007; 2009). Briefly, colour measurements of IMF samples were
229 performed using a tristimulus colorimeter (Minolta Chroma Meter CR300, Minolta
230 Corporation, NJ). The TPA and tensile test were carried out with a TA.XT2i SMS
231 Stable Micro Systems Texture Analyser (Stable Microsystems Ltd., Surrey, England)
232 using a cylindrical probe P/25 for TPA or a tensile grip (A/TGT) for the tensile test.
233 Texture tests were performed at about 22 °C just after opening the bags. The TPA was
234 determined in cylinders (1.5 cm high by 2 cm wide) and the tensile test was performed
235 on rectangular pieces (7.5 cm long, 2 cm wide and 0.3 cm thick) of IMF samples and
236 the resulting breaking strength was calculated, as previously described (Herrero,

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237 Ordóñez, Romero de Avila, Herranz, Hoz, & Cambero, 2007). The a_w was measured
238 using a Decagon CX1 hygrometer (Decagon Devices Inc., Pullman, WA, USA) at 25°C.
239 The sensory analyses involved a panel of twenty tasters (ten females and ten males)
240 selected from the members of the Departamento de Nutrición, Bromatología y
241 Tecnología de los Alimentos. A triangular test, a rank order test, and a descriptive test
242 were performed. The tests were carried in individual booths built according to the
243 International Standards Organization DP 66.58. (ISO, 1981) criteria. The analyses were
244 performed as described by Benedito, Cambero, Ortuño, Cabeza, Ordoñez, de la Hoz
245 (2011).

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247 *2.6. Statistical analysis*

248 The regression coefficients (R^2) of curves were calculated by Excel (Microsoft,
249 Redmond, Wash). Data obtained from chemical determinations, instrumental colour,
250 TPA and tensile test were statistically analyzed by a one-way ANOVA using a
251 Statgraphics Plus version 5.0 program.

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253 **3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

254 *3.1. Physic-chemical composition*

255 The general chemical composition of the products selected as IMF models is
256 shown in Table 1. In the context of the present work, the most important feature is the
257 values of a_w which was lower than 0.90, in all cases. As was mentioned above, this
258 parameter is low enough both to stabilize the final product from a technological point of
259 view and to avoid the growth of pathogenic bacteria. Accordingly, these products are
260 endowed with a very long shelf-life at room temperature without their sensory
261 properties being affected. The only spoilage agents that could act on the product are

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262 lipid oxidation, mould growth and excessive dehydration. However, these RTE-IMF are
263 usually vacuum packaged and, therefore, the above phenomena are effectively
264 prevented.

266 3.2. Safety aspects

267 As expected, the behaviour of bacteria against the action of E-beam fits first-
268 order inactivation kinetics yielding straight lines with very high regression coefficients
269 (R^2) (Table 2). This Table is also shows the survival equations and the D-values
270 obtained for the three strains in the different RTE-IMF products. *L. monocytogenes*
271 presented D-values (0.42 – 0.49) in the range of the data reported previously in other
272 meat products, such as cooked (Cabeza et al., 2007) and conventional dry-cured ham
273 (Hoz et al., 2008), broiler (Patterson, 1989), beef (Thayer & Boyd, 1995) and turkey
274 breast rolls (Zhu, Mendonca, Ismail, & Ahn, 2009) where D-values of 0.36 - 0.48 (six
275 strains), 0.42 kGy, 0.49 kGy, 0.44 kGy and 0.56 - 0.58 kGy, were reported respectively.
276 *L. innocua* presented higher D-values (0.46 - 0.57 kGy) than *L. monocytogenes*, which
277 confirms previous results in other meat products (Cabeza et al., 2007; Hoz et al., 2008)
278 concerning the use of *L. innocua* as a surrogate of *L. monocytogenes* for meat product
279 irradiation studies. In fact, *L. innocua* is also used as a surrogate of the pathogen listeria
280 in other bactericide treatments like thermal processing (Friedly, Crandall, Ricke,
281 O'Bryan, Martin, & Boyd, 2009) and pulsed light (Uesugi and Moraru, 2009).

282 The D-values (0.52 - 0.63) obtained here for *S. Typhimurium* in the three
283 matrixes (Table 2) are in total agreement with the results of other authors in a variety of
284 meat products (Cabeza et al., 2009; Grant and Petterson, 1992; Thayer, Boyd, Muller,
285 Lipson, Hayne, & Baer, 1990).

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286 The data about the resistance of *E. coli* O157:H7 against irradiation treatments
287 consistently offer lower D-values than those of *L. monocytogenes* and *S. Typhimurium*.
288 For instance, 0.24 - 0.30 kGy (5 strains) in ground beef (Clavero, Monk, Beuchat,
289 Doyle, & Brackett, 1994); 0.17 - 0.27 kGy in hamburger (Chirinos, Vizeu, Destro,
290 Franco, & Landgraf, 2002); 0.23 - 0.26 kGy in phosphate buffer (Sommers and
291 Rajkowski, 2008); 0.12 - 0.21 kGy and 0.22 - 0.31 in apple juice for non acid adapted
292 and acid adapted cells (Buchanan, Edelson, Snipes, & Boyd, 1998); 0.27 kGy in
293 chicken meat (Thayer & Boyd, 1993). In all cases, the recorded D-values were lower
294 than 0.30 kGy. The D-values shown in Table 2 (0.25 - 0.29 kGy) illustrates once more
295 the sensitivity of *E. coli* O157:H7 against irradiation and they confirm the data of
296 previous authors.

297 To calculate the dose of E-beam needed to achieve the FSO [the process
298 criterion (PrC)] in each RTE-IMF product, the highest D-value must be chosen, which
299 then has to be multiplied by the PeC (i.e. 2.39 D reductions) to yield the PrC. *E. coli*
300 O157:H7 is discarded in all cases since it presented the lowest D-values. In the Iberian
301 dry-cured ham and smoked tuna, *S. Typhimurium* was the highest radioresistant strain
302 with a D-value of 0.53 kGy and 0.63 kGy, respectively. Therefore, the PrC will be 1.27
303 kGy for the Iberian dry-cured ham and 1.51 kGy for the smoked tuna. *L. innocua*, the
304 surrogate of *L. monocytogenes*, presented the highest D-value (0.57 kGy) in the case of
305 the *cecina*. Then, the PrC will be 1.36 kGy. As the D-values of both species of *Listeria*
306 and *S. Typhimurium* are very close, a PrC of 1.5 kGy for IMF products could be
307 generalized. This treatment would cause about 3 D reductions of the load of salmonellae
308 and listeria and about 5 D reductions of *E. coli* O157:H7. The reduction of 5D is close
309 to the one proposed by ICMSF (2001) for cooking of beef patties with respect to *E. coli*
310 O157:H7, which was stated to be 4.4 reductions. From ICMSF data (2001), in

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311 frankfurters, a reduction of 3.39 D was calculated to achieve the criterion of “absence in
312 25 g” of *L. monocytogenes* cells by a thermal process, starting with an initial
313 contamination of 100 cells/g. In the case of salmonellae, the lowest infectious dose
314 recorded has been 28 cells (Vought & Tatini, 1998). This means that assuming an initial
315 contamination of 10 cells/g of this bacterium, 3 D reduction would lead to a final
316 number of 1/100g (4-fold lower than the microbiological criterion); a realistic level of
317 safety assuming a serving of 125 g. In summary, present findings both ensure the safety
318 of the final product and guarantee the lack of a positive result in the microbial
319 enrichment assays.

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321 *3.3. Rheological and sensorial aspects*

322 Table 3 shows the effect of E-beam irradiation on several quality parameters of
323 RTE-IMF. Results from the treatment with 3 kGy have been omitted since optimal
324 results occurred with the application of a dose lower than 2 kGy, namely, 1.5 kGy. In
325 smoked tuna, the decrease ($p < 0.05$) of redness was clearly observed during storage
326 (Table 3). Nevertheless, the behaviour of this colour parameter has to be related with the
327 fixation of the muscle pigment (myoglobin) instead of with the irradiation treatment
328 since no significant differences ($p > 0.05$) were found between treated and control
329 samples. However, a higher ($p < 0.05$) yellowness (b^* value) was observed when 3 kGy
330 was applied, i.e., 7.37 ± 0.70 at 0 kGy vs 9.03 ± 0.58 at 3 kGy (resumed data). In
331 contrast, in Iberian dry-cured ham, a higher red colour intensity was reflected by the
332 increase of the a^* parameter when 3 kGy was applied, i.e. 14.77 ± 1.70 at 0 kGy vs
333 18.46 ± 0.65 at 3 kGy (resumed data). Ahn, Kim, Jo, Lee, Yook, & Byun (2004)
334 reported that, in cured meat, there was a reduction of nitrosoheme pigments due to a
335 denitrosylation of NO-Mb in meat products, immediately after the ionizing treatments,

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336 but generally doses > 2 kGy are required to obtain significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in
337 the colour parameters of myofibrillar products. In the case of the *cecina*, there were no
338 significant changes in colour parameters during the shelf-life. Therefore, there were
339 practically no significant differences detected in the colour between irradiated samples
340 at a dose lower than 2 kGy and non-treated samples of the three RTE products.

341 In the texture features, a minor significant difference ($p < 0.05$) was found only
342 in the smoked tuna (Table 3). This affected the hardness, which was somewhat harder in
343 samples treated at both 1 and 2 kGy. Yoon (2003) has also reported an increase in
344 hardness of treated cooked chicken breast at 2.9 kGy. This author indicated that the
345 changes could be due to shrinkage of the myofibrils. However other authors have
346 reported that the texture of meat products are not affected by E-beam treatments at
347 doses ≤ 3 kGy (Cabeza et al., 2007; 2009; Hoz et al., 2008; Lee & Ahn, 2005). It may
348 be concluded that, in general, there are no changes in the quality parameters of the RTE-
349 IMF products studied here, when they are treated at 1 and 2 kGy.

350 In the sensory analysis, no significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) were detected in the
351 triangular analysis, when samples controls were compared with those treated with either
352 1 or 2 kGy, except for the odour in the smoked tuna, just after the treatment when 2 kGy
353 was applied; this disappeared after storage at 4 °C for 15 days (resumed data). These
354 results are in accordance with those obtained in the descriptive test. The differences
355 perceived in the odour of the smoked tuna were probably a consequence of the decrease
356 in the smoke curing odour and the release of a slight stale odour, as was confirmed
357 when the samples were treated at 3 kGy. Adverse sensory effects in several ionizing
358 treated muscle products have been reported (Brewer, 2009; Jo and Ahn, 2000; Medina
359 et al., 2009), which is explained by the different reactions that occur because of
360 ionizing; this generates an off-odour and flavour (Byun, Lee, Jo, YooK, 2001; Kwon,

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361 Known, Nam, Lee, Ahn, 2008). Off-odours of ionizing in treated products have been
362 associated to amino acid degradations (Jo & Ahn, 2000) and the generation of sulphur
363 compounds (Brewer, 2009; Yan, Lee, Nam, Min, & Ahn, 2006). Brewer (2009) found
364 that the ionizing treatment can induce formation of iso-octane-soluble carbonyl
365 compounds in the lipid fraction and low molecular weight, acid-soluble carbonyls, in
366 the protein fraction of meat. In the present work, the above mentioned changes were
367 undetected, neither in the instrumental nor sensory means. Higher doses of radiation
368 (e.g. > 2 kGy) are probably necessary to observe them. In fact, in the descriptive test,
369 differences ($p < 0.05$) were observed in odour at doses of 3 kGy, i.e.: reddish-brown and
370 bright colour decreases, smoke odour practically disappeared. Similarly, some
371 differences were also detected in flavour, such as a lower fishy flavour, a slight stale
372 and pungent flavours and a light loss of juiciness. However, no significant differences
373 ($p < 0.05$) were observed in the appearance attribute.

374

375 *3.4. Shelf-life of treated products*

376 The RTE- IMF products have a very long storage period because they are shelf-
377 stable. However, the shelf-life of smoked tuna was analyzed since, among the three, this
378 product is the one with the highest a_w (0.88). Table 4 shows the results. After 78 days of
379 storage, the bacteria count was lower than 10^4 c.f.u./g, even in the control batch. From a
380 sensory point of view, no differences were found. Since tuna contains long chain
381 unsaturated fatty acids, the most likely changes would be those derived from lipid
382 oxidation, growth of moulds or excessive dehydration but the vacuum packaging
383 avoided the progress of these phenomena.

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385 **4. CONCLUSIONS**

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386 The E-beam treatment of ready-to-eat intermediate moisture foods with doses of
387 1.5 kGy allows the food safety objective for *L. monocytogenes*, *S. Typhimurium* and *E.*
388 *coli* O157H7 to be achieved with practically no modifications of quality attributes.

389

390 **Acknowledgements**

391 The present work has been supported by the Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovacion
392 with Project CARNISENUSA (CSD2007-00016), included in the CONSOLIDER-
393 INGENIO 2010 issue and AGL2010-19158. We are grateful to IONISIOS for the
394 technical assistance provided during E-beam irradiation.

395

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2 Table 1. Selected chemical-physical parameters (\pm standard deviation) of RTE-IMF
3 (Iberian dry-cured ham, *Cecina* and Smoked tuna)

4

<i>IMF product</i>	Iberian dry-cured ham	<i>Cecina</i> (dry beef)	Smoked tuna
<i>Parameter</i>			
Dry matter (%)	55.70 \pm 0.70	54.07 \pm 0.37	43.46 \pm 3.23
Ash (%)	4.56 \pm 0.18	4.92 \pm 0.76	5.49 \pm 0.38
Fat (% D.M.)	29.20 \pm 0.43	23.93 \pm 0.35	3.47 \pm 0.77
pH	5.92 \pm 0.02	5.82 \pm 0.03	5.80 \pm 0.01
a_w	0.87 \pm 0.005	0.84 \pm 0.006	0.88 \pm 0.003

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1 Table 2. Irradiation decimal reduction values (D_{10}) for *Escherichia coli* O157:H7,
 2 *Listeria monocytogenes* Scott A, *Listeria innocua* and *Salmonella enterica* serovar
 3 Typhimurium in RTE-IMF slices
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Product	Organism	Survival equation [y = log c.f.u/g; x = dose (kGy)]	D_{10} (kGy)
Iberian dry-cured ham	<i>L. monocytogenes</i>	$y = -2.4100x + 8.7200$ ($R^2 = 0.99$)	0.42
<i>Cecina</i>	<i>L. monocytogenes</i>	$y = -2.0370x + 7.9497$ ($R^2 = 0.97$)	0.49
Smoked tuna	<i>L. monocytogenes</i>	$y = -2.3300x + 8.7421$ ($R^2 = 0.99$)	0.43
Iberian dry-cured ham	<i>L. innocua</i>	$y = -2.1200x + 9.2200$ ($R^2 = 0.99$)	0.47
<i>Cecina</i>	<i>L. innocua</i>	$y = -1.7663x + 6.8979$ ($R^2 = 0.98$)	0.57
Smoked tuna	<i>L. innocua</i>	$y = -2.1923x + 6.3657$ ($R^2 = 0.97$)	0.46
Iberian dry-cured ham	<i>S. Typhimurium</i>	$y = -2.1190x + 8.9820$ ($R^2 = 0.97$)	0.53
<i>Cecina</i>	<i>S. Typhimurium</i>	$y = -1.9281x + 7.6274$ ($R^2 = 0.99$)	0.52
Smoked tuna	<i>S. Typhimurium</i>	$y = -1.4961x + 7.0407$ ($R^2 = 0.95$)	0.67
Iberian dry-cured ham	<i>E.coli</i> O157:H7	$y = -3.8017x + 9.1295$ ($R^2 = 0.99$)	0.26
<i>Cecina</i>	<i>E.coli</i> O157:H7	$y = -4.0507x + 8.9945$ ($R^2 = 0.98$)	0.25
Smoked tuna	<i>E.coli</i> O157:H7	$y = -3.4295x + 8.9392$ ($R^2 = 0.98$)	0.29

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1 Table 3. Effects (average values) of E-beam treatment [0 (control), 1, and 2 kGy] on
 2 colour and rheological features of selected RTE-IMF products. Unless otherwise is
 3 stated no significant differences were found between control (untreated) and the treated
 4 samples.

5

Product	Dry-cured ham ¹	<i>Cecina</i>	Smoked tuna
Colour (CIELAB)			
<i>L</i> * (lightness)	44.10 ± 3.16*	29.16 ± 1.48*	46.01 ± 2.55*
	43.92 ± 3.32**	30.33 ± 1.67**	46.57 ± 2.29**
<i>a</i> * (redness)	16.08 ± 1.38*	9.06 ± 2.06*	12.92 ± 1.51*
	17.89 ± 1.89**	8.42 ± 2.17**	9.31 ± 1.89**
<i>b</i> * (yellowness)	11.81 ± 1.69*	2.72 ± 0.73*	7.89 ± 1.31*
	12.42 ± 1.09**	3.24 ± 1.09**	8.64 ± 1.21**
TPA analysis			
Hardness (N)	89.5 ± 27.8	43.67 ± 11.26	41.14 ± 6.95 ^a
Springiness (m)	0.057 ± 0.009	0.042 ± 0.01	0.0053 ± 0.008
Adhesiveness (N x s)	- 1.8 ± 0.9	-2.53 ± 0.11	- 0.35 ± 0.19
Cohesiveness (ratio)	0.45 ± 0.09	0.38 ± 0.03	0.523 ± 0.044
Gumminess (N)	40.27 ± 8.51	16.58 ± 6.61	21.62 ± 4.58
Chewiness (N x m)	2.30 ± 1.56	0.62 ± 0.03	0.12 ± 0.03
Breaking strength (N/m ²)	0.132 ± 0.06	0.113 ± 0.058	0.053 ± 0.008

6

7 ¹ The muscle *biceps femoris* dissected were used for the determinations.

8 *Value determined after 1 day of storage once the treatment was applied

9 **Value determined after 15 (smoked tuna) and 24 (Iberian dry-cured ham and *cecina*)
 10 days of storage at 4 °C once the treatment was applied

11 ^a Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) were found. The actual values for 0, 1 and 2 kGy
 12 were: 33.61±5.60^b, 44.72±6.17^{a,b} and 45.08±5.07^a N

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3 Table 4. Shelf-life of the control and E-beam treated (1 and 2 kGy) RTE smoked tuna.

4 Total viable count (log c.f.u./g) in plate count agar

0 kGy		1 kGy		2 kGy	
Storage days	Log c.f.u./g	Storage days	Log c.f.u./g	Storage days	Log c.f.u./g
0	0.46	0	N.A.	0	N.A.
16	2.94	16	0.76	16	N.A.
22	2.77	22	1.10	22	N.A.
29	3.19	29	2.85	29	N.A.
43	3.14	43	N.A.	43	0.59
51	3.17	51	2.49	51	2.72
78	3.91	78	2.89	78	2.39

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6 N.A.: Not analyzed.

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